

Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its Influence on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in FCT, Abuja

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Abstract

This study is on Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The purpose of this study therefore is to investigate students' Psycho-social Disposition and as it influences their achievement in mathematics. Three objectives and research questions guided this study. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970), a sample size of 384 respondents were randomly selected from school with total population of 24,771 students through simple random sampling techniques. Data was collected the use of two instruments. Mean score and standard deviation and t-test was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. All statistical analysis was conducted with a significant level of 0.05. There is a significant influence of students' attitudes on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja. It was recommended that Mathematics teachers should be creative in adopting various in the teaching and learning of mathematics so that the anxiety associated with mathematics can be controlled in such a way that learners develop the needed confidence that will improve their academic achievement.

Keywords; Psycho-socio Deposition, Attitude, Anxiety and academic achievement

Introduction

Mathematics like any other compulsory and examinable subject offered in both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria plays a key role in shaping how individuals deal with various spheres of private, social and civil life (Anthony & Walshaw, 2009). The Government of Nigeria acknowledges the importance of Mathematics and Sciences in achieving Sustainable Development Goals and in the attainment of the Vision 2030 as would provide the necessary manpower to steer the country into new technological and industrial development. This is evidenced by the concerted effort by the Government through the Ministry of Education to improve the performance both in primary and secondary mathematics through the implementation of SMASSE project. However, the low performance in the subject has persisted despite the desperate attempts to provide enough teachers, facilities and in-service training for teachers and provision of other necessary materials posing a lot of concerns to all stakeholders in Education. This implies that there are other factors at play that need to be further investigated. An analysis of performance in Basic Certificate Examination results below reveals that Mathematics is among the poorly performed subject which also is the case in most schools in the country.

All subjects have their areas of application in real life activities, but among them; Mathematics is the most important. Mathematics is a tool that can be used in our daily activities to provide solution to some difficulties faced in life. The knowledge of Mathematics is so relevant to the extent that it has been considered as one of the most important core subjects in the school curriculum. With the advancement in information communication technology, Mathematics has also gained more attention and importance. It is so necessary today for people of all ages to be effectively and efficiently knowledgeable in Mathematics for application and analysis of their works in order to be successful citizen in this information age (Petros, et.al; 2019).

Because of these immeasurable benefits of Mathematics in the society, the poor Mathematics achievement of students becomes a thing of concern in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The researcher has observed that achievement in mathematics is a function of many interrelated variables which can be grouped as student factors, school factors and home factors. Student factors are regarded by some researchers as a key factor to be taken into account when attempting to understand and explain the student achievement in Mathematics.

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In psychology, an attitude refers to a set of emotions, beliefs, and behaviours towards a particular object, person, things or event. Attitudes are often the result of experience or upbringing. While attitudes are enduring, they can also change (Kendra, 2022). Attitude takes into account of organization of concepts, beliefs, habits and motives associated with a particular object. The concepts and belief associated with an attitude are often referred to as the cognitive component of attitude, the habit as the action component, and motives as the affective component. Attitude can be understood as a tendency which prepares a person to behave in a certain way towards a specific object or a class of objects subjects to conditions prevailing in the environment (Mangal, 2019). Therefore, the way that one thinks, feels, and reacts express one's attitude towards a particular object and these are formed under different conditions.

For Mangal (2019) attitudes are formed under the condition of integration of experience, differentiation of experiences, and trauma of experience and adaptation of the available attitudes. In another words, attitude can be formed by an individual personally or by observing, imitating and learning from the environment. Mensah, et.al (2013) affirmed that attitude is seen as more or less positive and encompass emotions, belief, values and behavioral and hence affect individual way of thinking, acting and behaving which has a lot of implications to teaching and learning. Therefore, some students' disposition towards Mathematics could be positive or negative which probably are determinants of high or low achievement in Mathematics.

The researcher observed that students' attitudes towards Mathematics probably influence the achievement of student in Mathematics. Some students view Mathematics as their Waterloo, as a result, they perform poorly in Mathematics. The attitude of the student apparently showed that Mathematics is a difficult and boring subject and this tends to make students develop lesser interest and lose confidence in Mathematics.

Dowker, et.al (2016) expressed that Mathematics anxiety is another students' attitude, which is a feeling of tension that interferes with students' abilities in solving Mathematical problems and that Mathematics anxiety could be traced to the students own learning experiences in school. Belbase (2013) explained that when one thinks about Mathematics anxiety, two things may come to one's mind, one is 'anxiety as a progressive thinking' and the other is 'anxiety as a regressive thinking'. All anxiety is not worthless things. Therefore, some students seem to experience progressive thinking when they are puzzling in a Mathematics problem for a few days and trying to solve it in a variety of ways without losing passion. Then certainly it is a good thing. Anxiety is mostly taken as regressive thinking in the situation where some students tend to have anxiety and trying to go away or get rid of Mathematical problem simply by avoiding it and taking it negatively. For instance, where the subject performance in most cases is ranked the last, students appear to associate the subject with failures. They see the nature of Mathematics to cause panic, unnecessary anxiety, fear and hatred during Mathematics lesson. Some get nervous to ask questions during classes and see working on their assignment as a stressful task. Mostly, they feel tensed when preparing for a Mathematics tests, quizzes and examinations. As a result, they tend to avoid and ignore the subject and probably prefer to engage in other activities that they anticipate will result in reward (Dowker, et.al 2016).

Poor Mathematics achievement of students in internal and external Examination is a reflection of the problem and challenges facing the educational system in Nigeria today and Federal Capital Territory, Abuja in particular. These poor students' Mathematics achievement has been of great concern to parents, teachers, counselors, school administrators, curriculum planners, students themselves and researchers. Despite the availability of suitable teaching facilities, qualified and competent teachers, all guidance programs and counseling strategies, conducive environment, regular payment of teachers' salaries and parental involvement to improve students' Mathematics achievement, poor Mathematics achievement are recorded yearly in senior secondary schools FCT, Abuja and this has become necessary to find out the variables that influence such poor achievement (Belbase, 2013). Poor Mathematics achievement usually brings about sadness and frustration to the individual concerned and to his or her parents as well as other education stakeholders. There has been wide cry each year for poor achievement when WAEC or NECO releases their annual results. Candidates' achievement at the Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) conducted by WAEC and NECO has consistently remained poor in Mathematics.

Student attitudes towards Mathematics appear to be responsible for these ugly trends as they are key factors that probably influence Mathematics achievement. The disposition that Mathematics is difficult, logical and boring seem to make students think they cannot understand mathematics and that Mathematics is meant for only talented students. Alphine (2015) conducted research on students' attitudes and their effects on learning and achievement in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Kikuyu Kiambu County, Kenya. The objectives of the study are to determine the perception of students about Mathematics in public secondary schools in Kiambu county, to examine the factors influencing students' attitudes towards mathematics, to investigate how the students' attitudes affect their learning and achievement in mathematics and to seek recommendations on how to improve students' attitudes towards learning and achievement in Mathematics. The sample size

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was 140 students from seven sampled schools with about 700 form four students. The sampled schools were selected using multi-stage sampling methods so as to bring about the expected variability, make the sample more representative.

Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The main instrument used for the study was questionnaire. The percentages obtained were used in making comparisons and conclusion. The result obtained was presented using bar chart. Also, the results of the previous grades of the students from end of the term were used to gauge their performance in Mathematics. The result indicated that the students have positive attitude towards Mathematics and therefore expected to perform better.

Jerry, et.al (2019) carried out a study on The Effects of Mathematics Anxiety on the Achievement of Senior Secondary Two Students in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent at which Mathematics anxiety affects students' achievement in Mathematics and to suggest ways of raising students interest in Mathematics. The targeted group for the study comprised of all co-educational Governments owned senior Secondary schools in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The population for the study consisted of all 4,234 Senior Secondary two students within Jos North Local Government of Plateau State. Random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 120 students made up of 30 from each of the for selected secondary schools used for this study. Survey research design was adopted. Two instruments were used for data collection. A Mathematics Anxiety Scale Questionnaire (MASQ) adopted from Driscoll structured to elicit information required by the research question and it was based on a four-points scale. The rule used to distinguish between significance and insignificance of the responses was the average four –points scale which is below 2.50. Any mean score up to 2.50 and above is regarded as positive while any mean score below 2.50 is regarded negative. Achievements were measured by using scores already awarded or the students' mock examination which was the reason the researcher selected SS2 for this study because of all co-educational Government s owned senior secondary schools Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State do sit for mock examination in SS2. The data collected were analyzed using average percent and chi square statistic. The research was answered using mean and standard deviation while the research hypothesis was done using SPSS package. The result showed that students agreeing that Mathematics anxiety to large extent exist among them because all the statements have mean score greater than the cutoff point of 2.50. This implies that all students generally agreed that Mathematics anxiety exist among students and has great effects on their achievement in Mathematics.

Fung et al (2018), carried out a study on student Engagement and Mathematics Achievement: Unravelling main and interactive effects. The study explored the relationship between student engagement and Mathematics achievement. The population of 295,416 from 11,767 secondary schools in 34 countries who participated in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012. Only school students aged between 15years 3months and 16years 2months at the beginning of the PISA assessment period were invited to participate in PISA 2012. This study used data from PISA 2012 PISA 2012 was sponsored and administered internationally by PISA International consortium. The respondents' preferences were determined using a four –points scale, Three-level (students, school and country level) HLM was used to examined the main effect of different pairwise combination of engagement. Students in countries were sampled using a two-stage strategy. From each of the school sampled, 35 students or fewer were sampled with equal probability from a list of all students within the school. Independent samples t-tests were next employed to address research objective 2 of the study, namely to examine whether students benefited from having higher levels of engagement in two different components simultaneously. The result showed that components of students' engagement (affective, behavioural, and cognitive) were individually related to their Mathematics achievement. A comparison of the HLM results for the relationship between different components of students' engagement and their achievement showed that students 'behavioural engagement, as measured by their participation in different Mathematics learning activities inside and outside the classroom, made only a small difference to their achievement when compared to those for affective or cognitive engagement. The above study was conducted over the shore of Nigeria to explore the relationship between student engagement and Mathematics achievement. While the present study is aim at investigate the influence of student attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. Using the component of students' attitudes towards Mathematics, mathematics anxiety and behavioral-engagement of students on Mathematics to justified Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Objectives of the Study

Specially, the study sought to;

1. Examine the influence of students' attitudes towards Mathematics achievement in senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

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2. To determine the influence of mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
3. Assess the influence of behavioral-engagement of students on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does students' attitude towards Mathematics influence the achievement in Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?
2. To what extent does Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?
3. To what extent does behavioural-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
2. There is no significant influence of Mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
3. There is no significant influence of behavioural-engagement on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of this study is 24,771 of 77 public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja. The sample for the study was 384 students using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling table. Simple random sampling technique was used. Two self-structure question was used. The questionnaire was designed to find out the extent of Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of secondary school students. The instrument was divided into four sections A, B and C. Section A covers 1-10 on students' attitude. Section B takes care of items 11-20 on students' Mathematics anxiety while Section C was from items 21-30 on students behavioral-engagement on Mathematics. The responses were on the continuum of four-point rating scale. The instruments yielded logical validity indices of 0.83 and 0.74 and resulted to an average index of 0.79. with a reliability index of 0.81. The data collected would be analyzed using mean score and standard deviation and t-test would be used to test the formulated null hypotheses. All statistical analysis was conducted with a significant level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does students' attitude towards Mathematics influence the achievement in Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the extent to which Students' Attitude Towards Mathematics influence the achievement of Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
1	Learning mathematics requires much effort.	2.87	0.82	Agree
2	Mathematics is a boring subject.	3.05	1.19	Agree
3	On my own I can take initiative in learning Mathematics.	2.91	0.96	Agree
4	I do not have mathematics abilities and skills to solve complex problems.	2.56	1.11	Agree
5	There is no sex difference in understanding Mathematics	2.67	1.16	Agree
6	I do not require high knowledge and performance in mathematics to excel	2.98	0.78	Agree
7	I believe I can understand the content in the mathematics courses.	2.92	1.01	Agree
8	Mathematics is important in our daily interactions	2.67	1.08	Agree
9	I rate mathematics equally high as other core subjects	2.94	0.96	Agree
10	Mathematics is useful in life.	2.79	1.01	Agree
	Average mean	2.84	1.01	

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Table 1 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which students' attitude towards mathematics influence the achievement in mathematics of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.84. This value is above the accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that students' attitude towards mathematics has high influence on achievement in mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

Research Question 2

To what extent does Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the Extent to which Mathematics Anxiety Influence Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
11	Anxiety and fear grip my mind during mathematics lesson.	2.87	0.82	Agree
12	I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	2.79	1.02	Agree
13	I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	2.83	1.00	Agree
14	Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	2.81	1.08	Agree
15	I believe I can learn well in a mathematics course.	2.99	0.82	Agree
16	I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	2.65	1.00	Agree
17	I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my math's examinations.	3.10	0.82	Agree
18	I get panicked due to constant failure in mathematics examinations.	3.26	0.76	Agree
19	I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses	2.60	1.14	Agree
20	I feel confident enough to ask questions in my mathematics class	2.84	0.85	Agree
	Average mean	2.87	0.93	

Table 2 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement in senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.87. This value is above the accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that Mathematics anxiety has a high influence of Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja

Research Question 3

To what extent does behavioural-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the Extent to which Behavioural-Engagement Influence Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
21	I pay attention in mathematics classes.	2.87	0.82	Agree
22	I work hard on my mathematics homework.	2.56	1.11	Agree
23	I avoid any form of distractions when studying mathematics	2.67	1.16	Agree
24	I enjoy talking about mathematics problems with friends	2.98	0.78	Agree
25	I study hard for mathematics tests.	2.92	1.01	Agree
26	I find it pleasurable participating in mathematics competitions.	2.67	1.08	Agree
27	I do mathematics more than other subjects two hours daily outside school.	3.10	0.82	Agree
28	I always have confidence when I want to attempt mathematics	3.26	0.76	Agree
29	I do not always study hard for test and examinations and I have been having poor grade.	2.60	1.14	Agree
30	I persevered until I understand mathematics contents,	2.84	0.85	Agree
	Average mean	2.85	0.95	

Table 3 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which behavioral-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school of FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.85. This value is above the

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accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that behavioral-engagement has a high influence on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school in FCT, Abuja

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja.

Table 4: t-test Statistic showing the Influence of Students' Attitudes on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students, FCT, Abuja

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Students Attitude	384	2.84	1.01	383	56.33	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 indicates the significance of influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of chi-square statistics is 56.33 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of calculated t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant influence of Mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja.

Table 5: T-Test Statistic showing the Influence of Mathematics Anxiety on Mathematics Achievement of Senior

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Mathematics Anxiety	384	2.87	0.93	383	65.24	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

Secondary School FCT, Abuja

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 indicates the significance of influence of mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of t-test statistics is 65.24 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of mathematics anxiety on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant influence of behavioural-engagement on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

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Table 6: T-Test Statistic showing the Significant Influence of Behavioral-Engagement on Mathematics achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in CT, Abuja.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Behavioural Engagement	384	2.85	0.95	383	56.33	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 indicates the significance of influence of behavioural-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of t-test statistics is 56.33 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of calculated of t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of behavioural-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study have been discussed based on the hypothesis. The finding from hypothesis one reveal that there is a significant influence of students' attitudes on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja. This finding is in agreement with findings from the study of Alphine (2015) which showed that students' attitude had significant effects on learning and achievement in mathematics in public secondary schools in Kikuyu Kiambu County, Kenya. Mensah et al (2013) further noted that if positive attitude is developed towards Mathematics, high academic performance could be achieved. This positive attitude in this regard is a valid objective of mathematics education; it owns that if nurtured, the students' feelings would interact and influence the mental abilities and thereby having positive influence on learning and achievement of the subject. Students' attitudes towards Mathematics determine the success in the subject, their ability, willingness to learn the subject, and to work on variety of assigned tasks available. In general, the conceptions students hold about Mathematics determines how they approach Mathematics tasks leading them into either productive or non-productive orientations. In many cases, students have been found to approach Mathematics as procedural and rule oriented. This prevents them from experiencing the richness of Mathematics and the many approaches that could be used to develop competence in the subject (Alphine, 2015).

The findings from hypothesis two revealed there is a significant influence of mathematics anxiety on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. This finding is similar to those of Jerry, et al (2019) which showed significant Effects of Mathematics Anxiety on the Achievement of Senior Secondary Two Students in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. Mutegei, et al (2021) in their findings discovered there is a significant relationship between mathematics Anxiety, attitude and performance among secondary school students in Embu, Kenya.

The findings from hypothesis three indicates there is a significant influence of behavioral-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Findings from Manmin, et al. (2021) showed that there was a significant influence of Student Engagement on Mathematical Achievement among Secondary School Students in Selangor, Malaysia. In addition, Manmin, et al., (2021) showed in their findings showed there was a significant relationship between student engagement and mathematics achievement. More so, Dylmoon, et al (2019) asserted that Student behavioral engagement contributes to meaningful learning. If students are behaviorally engaged, they will be involved during the class, and they have a sense of belonging to the class. This sense of belonging will make students experience the enjoyment of learning, recognize the meaning of learning, and not only come to the class just for getting by. It is the goal of a classroom as a learning community Dylmoon et al, 2019). On the contrary, if students are not engaged in the classroom, they lose the opportunity to learn more.

Conclusion

The study concludes that attitudes can have powerful influence over behaviour; while attitudes are enduring, they can also change. Mathematics anxiety could be traced to the students' own learning experiences in school. Students, who are behaviorally-engaged, work hard on Mathematics homework, discuss Mathematics problems with friends, attend classes

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regularly and put more effort in their school work. They are more capable of overcoming initial difficulties and connecting their learning to individual mathematical concepts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the researcher recommends that:

1. Students in public senior secondary schools in the FCT, Abuja should be sensitized through workshops and seminars on the need to develop a positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics so as to ensure there is improvement in their academic achievement in mathematics.
2. Mathematics teachers should be creative in adopting various in the teaching and learning of mathematics so that the anxiety associated with mathematics can be controlled in such a way that learners develop the needed confidence that will improve their academic achievement.
3. Learners should be actively engaged in school and at home with a series of mathematical problems. They should be continuously drilled until they develop interest in the subject for the purpose of improving their academic achievement.

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